

Impairment of Tactile Acuity Under Chemical Stimulation of Thermoreceptors

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Abstract. Tactile acuity is found to be reduced by capsaicin-induced nociception. This suggests that nociception stimulation can worsen spatial touch sensitivity. However, the activation of nociceptive pathways may possibly be unnecessary. Milder stimulation may alter tactile acuity without causing inflammation. In this study, we used oregano and menthol to selectively activate thermoreceptors that respond to mild thermal stimuli to investigate their influence on tactile acuity. The results revealed an increase in the two-point discrimination threshold after stimulation with the warm and cold receptors. These observations suggest that mild chemically induced stimuli impair tactile acuity.

Keywords: Tactile acuity · Chemical stimulation · Psychophysics.

1 Introduction

Tactile acuity has been found to be impaired by capsaicin-induced nociceptive stimulation [3]. This phenomenon has been interpreted as activation of the TRPV1 receptor and resulting pain impairing spatial discrimination ability. However, this explanation left open the possibility that more moderate stimulation might modulate tactile acuity without inducing inflammation. The modulation of tactile acuity under mild stimulation provides evidence that strong nociceptive stimulation is unnecessary. This study aimed to explore the effect of mild thermal stimulation on tactile acuity. Traditional devices provide thermal stimulation through heat exchange with the skin. This method requires contact with the skin, which means that, in addition to generating the desired thermal stimuli, additional pressure is caused by skin contact. We wanted to avoid this additional pressure from skin contact in our experiments. Therefore, in this study, we used chemicals to activate thermoreceptors that respond to mild thermal stimuli. We used oregano and menthol to stimulate the TRPV3 and TRPM8 receptors that respond to moderate thermal stimuli from 25°C to 39°C [2].

2 Experiment

2.1 Material and Methods

The study participants were 11 males aged 21–31. The participants placed their right forearm on a table, and the chemicals were applied to their right volar forearm in a

randomized order. Salad oil was used as a placebo because it does not specifically activate thermoreceptors. To stimulate warm receptors, pure oregano oil (R V Essential) was used (written as “warm”) because carvacrol in oregano is known for its specific activation of TRPV3 [5]. For cold receptors, menthol oil (Komamori, 30% menthol concentration) was applied to specifically activate TRPM8 (written as “cold”). Additionally, we mixed oregano and menthol in a 1:1 ratio, and this condition is written as “mix”. Using eye dropper pipettes and cotton swabs, 0.5 mL of these oils were uniformly applied to a 40 × 40 mm area on the proximal forearm. The two-point discrimination threshold (2PDT) was measured 15 min after application. To assess the 2PDT, a Vernier caliper was employed. The caliper was modified to include two probes attached to its jaws, each of which comprised a resin cylinder with a 3 mm diameter. Care was taken to ensure simultaneous contact of both cylinders with the skin during stimulation. The duration of each stimulation was set to 2 s. For the evaluation, stimuli with point-to-point distances ranging from 0 to 100 mm, increasing in increments of 10 mm, were applied. A 0 mm distance indicated a single-point stimulus applied along the proximal-distal axis of the forearm. Each distance was tested 20 times in a randomized order. The stimulation site near the elbow was consistently positioned at the midpoint of the stimulus’ edge, closest to the elbow. Participants with closed eyes entered the number of perceived points (1 or 2) on a keyboard. Each condition involved 220 stimuli administered at a minimum of 5-second intervals. The entire measurement process lasted 20 min, with a 2-minute break halfway through. To avoid the influence of previous conditions, as suggested by a pilot study indicating a return to baseline after one hour, a minimum two-hour interval was maintained between the two conditions. The experimental procedures were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Osaka University and were conducted in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

2PDT was determined for each condition individually. The 2PDT of every participant was estimated using logistic regression, fitting the data to a psychometric curve. A series of paired t-tests were performed to compare the thresholds for the four different stimulation conditions.

2.2 Results

The results are depicted in Fig. 1. The 2PDT values for Placebo, Warm, Cold, and Mix were 32.76 mm, 42.29 mm, 41.94 mm, and 49.90 mm, respectively. The paired t-tests were statistically significant in most comparisons ($p < 0.05$), except between Warm and Cold. The Mix condition presented a higher threshold than the other conditions ($p < 0.001$). The results indicated that stimulating warm and cold receptors increased the two-point discrimination.

3 Discussion and Conclusion

Tactile acuity is modulated by nociceptive stimulation [3]. This study investigated the need for strong nociceptive stimulation when modifying tactile acuity. We observed an impairment in tactile acuity resulting from the chemically induced warm and cold stimulations, whereas no inflammation was induced. This result suggests that the activation of nociceptive pathways is unnecessary.

Fig. 1. Results. (A) Fitted psychometric curves to the perceived number in Placebo (gray), Warm (pink), Cold (blue), and Mix (green) conditions ($n = 11$, average in bold). (B) Boxplots for the conditions.

Some people might consider that applying warm and cold stimuli can centrally trigger nociceptive pathways through an unmasking mechanism [1], resulting in reduced tactile acuity. However, none of the participants reported pain during our experiment, indicating no nociception was triggered. Thus, the unmasking mechanism does not explain our findings. Alternatively, tactile acuity impairment may occur without stimulation of nociceptive pathways. Wide Dynamic Range (WDR) neurons in the spinal cord can respond to innocuous warm and cold stimuli [4]. WDR neurons may serve as relay nuclei with projections that accommodate warm and cold stimuli and play a role in modulating tactile acuity.

Notice that 2PDT values were close to the side length of the smeared area (40 mm), suggesting a potential influence of the smeared area. In future studies, we will investigate how chemicals' concentration and smear area influence tactile acuity.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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